

A synthetic machine learning framework for complex crystallization processes: The case study of the second-order asymmetric transformation of enantiomers

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ABSTRACT

Improving the flexibility and capabilities of pharmaceutical technologies and lowering the process development time while satisfying regulatory constraints translate to highly desired resilient supply chains. Generating and validating the necessary knowledge *in-silico* before experimentation or plant-scale intervention with minimized human implications is the dream this paper aims to contribute to. The idea is demonstrated through the case study of particle size-controlled second-order asymmetric transformation of enantiomers (SOAT), a crystallization and racemization-based resolution technique. The fundamental processes form a complex network, to which we propose a crystallization-integrated wet milling system, which is promising but has limited general, and no SOAT-specific operation experience. The developed computational framework has three steps: (1) skilled scientists draft potential technologies to solve a well-defined problem; (2) all alternatives are modeled with high fidelity first-principle models, followed by high throughput parametric optimizations (3) data mining is deployed to extract key information from the synthetic database of optimal solutions and take the effectiveness of process design and operation to the next level. In this work, population balance-based models were applied to describe the crystallization, fragmentation, and chemical reaction in the crystallizer and wet mill. The efficient implementation enabled the execution of nearly 1300 global multiobjective process optimizations. Carefully trained classifiers consistently predicted the with or without milling and with or without *T*-cycling decisions (AUC score exceeding 0.85). Regression methods estimated the product property profile with Pearson coefficients over 0.95. The results agree with the existing SOAT literature based on a literature meta-analysis, but some of the conclusions point beyond the state-of-the-art.

1. Introduction

Crystallization is a key operation in the pharmaceutical industry, a separation and purification method suitable for simultaneous particle formation. This last feature increased its importance, as particle properties impact the product behavior (bioavailability through polymorphism and dissolution rate through particle size) and the downstream operations (through particle size and shape). Hence, a massive effort was focused on efficiently designing and conducting pharmaceutical crystallization processes. The guidelines of leading regulatory agencies promoting the application of process analytical technologies (PAT) pointed beyond a broader crystallization process understanding. They brought the spring of feedback control strategies

and applied process modeling [32]. This latter was also fueled by the advances in computing infrastructures [14,35]. The vast landscape of possibilities opened doors to the solution of more challenging problems; a recent one is the control of *enantio*-purity.

The problem of adverse effects of enantiomers got attention after the Thalidomide crisis in the mid-20th century when racemic thalidomide was used to treat, amongst others, anxiety, sleep issues, and morning sickness. The (*R*) enantiomer delivered the desired sedative effect, whereas the (*S*)-enantiomer harbored embryo-toxic and teratogenic effects, resulting in thousands of severe birth defects and miscarriages. Since this disaster, ensuring *enantio*-purity has become paramount for active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs). Alternatives to achieve homochiral products include biochemical syntheses, stereoselective

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Fig. 1. Schematics of SOAT in CWM: the external mill breaks the large particles of both enantiomer crystals (green squares and blue circles) to enhance the dissolution and crystallization rates in the crystallizer, which subsequently accelerates the reaction, hence, the de-racemization.

catalysis, or the separation of enantiomers from racemic mixtures. The separation pathway is often implemented due to the challenges associated with stereoselective syntheses. Chiral chromatography is a robust separation option, but it is hardly scalable and is relatively expensive. The diastereomer salt formation is a multistep process, where a salt is formed with an *enantio*-pure compound to obtain different *L* and *D* enantiomer salt solubilities, allowing their separation *via* crystallization. Finally, the compound of interest is freed from the salt in *enantio*-pure form. Preferential crystallization is a single-step option for conglomerate forming systems, which allows the development of advanced technologies to obtain both enantiomers simultaneously, with far-reaching operation-related implications [10]. These separations share the yield limitation risen by the loss of the antipode. The emergence of liquid phase racemization opens a more straightforward way. Racemization reaction compensates the solute concentration depletion at the expense of the antipode during a preferential crystallization. This is called SOAT, which can achieve complete de-racemization [39], and it is known to be enhanced by small particles. Beyond grinding, *T*-cycling was proposed as a convenient, scalable process intensification, which relies on secondary nucleation [6,7]. It was demonstrated that SOAT does not necessarily require *T*-cycling. A cooling-only process can result in complete de-racemization significantly faster than the *T*-cycling induced de-racemization under certain kinetic conditions (a productivity gain of one hundred was reported). Nevertheless, this strategy is not robust against the enantiomer purity degradation effects of random primary nucleation of the undesired enantiomer [25].

Two significant problems still need to be addressed. Firstly, *enantio*-purity is not the sole critical quality attribute (CQA) of APIs: particle size, shape, and polymorphism often possess high importance [24]. The second is the *T*-cycling itself. Its fine particle-producing ability is limited by thermodynamics (solubility), the associated energy demand is high, and its implementation at scale may face difficulties [31]. Steeply different yet practical intensification is needed for wide-scale implementation. Sonocrystallization and crystallization integrated wet milling (CWM) are emerging candidates [23,40]. Wet milling has already found industrial applications as a terminal particle size-correcting operation [21]. Recently, the integrated operation was proposed to broaden the attainable particle property space [34]. Despite the potential for simultaneous particle property and *enantio*-purity control with low energy demand, only a handful of studies analyzed this technology for SOAT. Designing such a complex process and system remains challenging. Hence, a vastly different knowledge generation that avoids lengthy and costly experimentation and is suitable for early-stage

technology screening is required.

Machine learning (ML) enabled unprecedented breakthroughs in science and technology, from computer vision [20] to secondary protein structure determination [18]. It is a handy tool if a sufficiently large training dataset is available, which brings the process engineers to the data-information paradox. If one has enough data for these data-hungry algorithms (a sample being a well-designed crystallization process), one probably already knows enough about the process. The current state-of-the-art implication of ML in crystallization engineering focuses on hybrid models [41] and enhanced monitoring [13]. Operation or design-relevant knowledge extraction has yet to be applied, except for recent attempts to extrapolate measured data [42]. The natural question arises at this point: what if the predictive power of high-fidelity first principle models were exploited to generate synthetic data in a high-throughput manner? These models incorporate the underlying physics making the synthetic dataset realistic.

This study has two goals. First, to address the important question quantitatively of whether batch CWM can be a successful process intensification for SOAT in comparison with the batch crystallization process (and if so, under which circumstances and how those circumstances can be predicted). Second, to develop a hybrid mechanistic modeling-ML framework and deploy it to solve the first objective. This incorporates generating a database of optimal solutions, where key process and kinetic parameters are varied, and subsequent data mining for knowledge extraction. Finally, a brief meta-analysis validates the case study and the new framework.

2. Methodology

2.1. The concept

Batch CWM found recent applications in pharmaceutical crystallization for particle size and shape control, with significant but unexploited potential to host SOAT processes, except for a handful of pioneering, qualitative studies on continuous, isothermal crystallization [19]. The high-shear wet mill generates a large number of fine particles that may trigger the Viedma ripening. Furthermore, it has been shown that the CWM operation can be synchronized to extend the attainable particle size and shape domain significantly. This projects that integrating chemical purity and product particle property may be feasible in CWMs (see Fig. 1).

Many design variables influence this process, including the initial conditions (concentrations, liquid phase EE, solid phase EE, seeding)

Fig. 2. Ternary phase diagram representing a conglomerate forming system at a given temperature. The phase limits change with the temperature.

and the dynamic crystallizer and mill operation. It would have been an extreme effort to design the system experimentally from scratch. The design space is probably narrow; hence, it is unlikely to find it with several preliminary experiments. This makes it a good case for the concept of this paper: artificial knowledge and *a priori* operation experience generation through data mining.

2.2. Kinetic modeling of the second-order asymmetric transformation

Secondary nucleation, crystal growth, dissolution, and racemization are assumed to occur in the crystallizer and the wet mill. That being said, the mean residence time of the slurry in the wet mill is significantly lower than in the crystallizer. Despite all mechanisms being considered, the wet mill population dynamics is expected to be governed by fragmentation, which is neglected in the crystallizer. An instant slurry transfer is assumed (no transport delay, crystallization, or reaction in the pipes). Since the macroscopic balance equations are relatively well-known, these are listed in this paper's Appendix, and here we present the kinetic model.

The kinetics depend on the relative supersaturation (σ), having positive values for supersaturated, and negative for undersaturated conditions. Expressing the solubility is straightforward in a single-component crystallization, but in the case of conglomerates, ternary phase diagrams are used to illustrate the potential phases and to calculate the solubilities of the enantiomers (see Fig. 2). The L and D enantiomers and the solvents represent the triangle's angles in the ternary phase diagram. The internal lines divide the diagram into four zones: a one-phase system exists closest to the Solvent angle. The solution is undersaturated to both enantiomers within this region. There are two, two-phase regions, where the solution is supersaturated for one, but undersaturated for the other enantiomer. The remaining part is the three-phase domain.

The discussion above underlined that an enantiomer's solubility depends on the counter enantiomer's concentration. Calculating the driving force is possible using the ternary phase diagrams directly. Notwithstanding, it was observed that simpler empirical equations could be applied to certain systems [9,27]. For the sake of simplicity, keeping in mind the limited generality, we implement the empirical model from the literature [27], where the solubility of the enantiomer i ($c_{s,i}$) depends on temperature and antipode concentration (c_j), and is described as:

$$c_{s,i} = a_0 \exp(a_1 T) + a_2 c_j \quad (1)$$

Both primary and secondary nucleation (B_p , and, respectively, $B_{p,i}$) are considered and described with the following equations:

$$B_{p,i} = k_p \sigma_i^p \exp\left(-\frac{E_p}{RT_K}\right) \quad (2)$$

$$B_{s,i} = k_s \sigma_i^s V_C \quad (3)$$

Crystal growth (G) and dissolution (D) are considered supersaturation and temperature dependent:

$$G_i = k_g \sigma_i^g \exp\left(-\frac{E_G}{RT_K}\right) \quad (4)$$

$$D_i = k_d (-\sigma_i)^d \exp\left(-\frac{E_D}{RT_K}\right) \quad (5)$$

A first-order liquid-phase racemization reaction is considered. The overall apparent reaction rate (r_i) for the enantiomer i can be written as:

$$r_i = k_r (c_j - c_i) \exp\left(-\frac{E_R}{RT_K}\right) \quad (6)$$

The $(c_j - c_i)$ indicates that enantiomer i is consumed when transformed into enantiomer j , and *vice-versa*.

The typical 3-stage mill configuration (e.g., IKA MagicLab) is modeled as a cascade of independent mills. The selection function provides the rate of breakage of L size crystals, whose size dependency is approximated with the tangent-hyperbolic selection function [29]:

$$S(L) = k_{br} (\tanh(k(L - L_c)) + 1) \quad (7)$$

where L_c is a critical crystal size under which the breakage vanishes, k governs the sharpness of breakage rate decay at L_c size, and k_{br} the breakage rate constant. The widely used scale-up criteria of high-shear wet mills is the shear rate (N_{sh}):

$$N_{sh} = \frac{\pi \omega^2 N_S N_R D_r}{d} \quad (8)$$

where ω is the rotation speed, N_R and N_S are the numbers of slots in the rotor and the stator, respectively, D_r is the rotor diameter, and d is the horizontal gap between the rotor and the stator. This description allows accounting for different head configurations directly. Here we relate the breakage rate to the shear rate with a linear function:

$$k_{br} = k_{br,0} N_{sh} \quad (9)$$

Finally, the breakage function (b) is expressed as a conditional probability, providing the number of L -size crystals from the breakage of λ -size crystals. It is modeled with a gamma distribution:

$$b(L|\lambda) = \frac{\beta^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha)} L^{\alpha-1} \exp(-\beta L) \quad (10)$$

with α and β shape and rate parameters. The kinetic Eqs. (1)-(10) are embedded into the macroscopic models. The fixed kinetic constants and parameters of these equations are listed in Appendix 2. A fair warning is necessary here. We implemented widely used kinetic equations for all mechanisms described above, but many rate equations were proposed and applied successfully on different crystallization systems [33]. A straightforward extension of this study should consider libraries of these equations, as different combinations would inherently translate to dynamic information-rich databases.

The crystallizer and the wet mill are described with two populations and mass balance equations. Furthermore, an energy balance is formulated for the wet mill considering the heating effects of the high-shear rotors. The partial and ordinary differential equations system is solved with a high-resolution finite volume method, implemented in C, and compiled to a dynamically linked library (.dll) using Visual Studio 2017.

Table 1
Optimization objectives with their weight factors.

O_i	w_i	Explanation
$\left \frac{\mu_{3,p,L} - \mu_{3,p,D}}{\mu_{3,p,L} + \mu_{3,p,D}} \right $	1	maximization of EE. $\mu_{3,p}$ is the third moment of product CSD
$-D_{10}$	0.1	maximization of D_{10} (mixture of L and D crystal populations)
$\frac{D_{90} - D_{10}}{D_{50}}$	1	minimization of the span (width) of the product size distribution (mixture of L and D crystal populations)
$\int_0^{t_m} \omega dt$	$9 \cdot 10^{-7}$	minimization of the mill utilization. ω represents the milling rate profile
$\sum_i (\omega_i - \omega_{i-1})^2$	$2 \cdot 10^{-5}$	ensures smooth milling profile and penalizes milling cycles
$\sum_i (T_i - T_{i-1})^2$	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$	ensures smooth temperature profile and penalizes T -cycles

Table 2
Optimization bounds and constraints.

Constraint or bound	Explanation
$T_{in} - 1 \geq T_i \geq T_f = 20$	the temperature bounds are set based on the initial (T_{in}) and final temperature (T_f)
$\omega_M = 300 \geq \omega_i \geq 0$	the milling rates are bounded with a maximal value (ω_M)
$t_f > t_{T,i} > t_{T,i-1} > 0$; $t_{\omega,i} > t_{\omega,i-1} > 0$	the sampling time instances must increase and fall into the $[0, t_f]$ interval.
$h_{r,M} = 0.5 \geq \frac{T_i - T_{i-1}}{t_{T,i} - t_{T,i-1}} \geq c_{r,M} = -0.5$	the heating and cooling rate are bounded by maximal heating ($h_{r,M}$) and cooling rates $c_{r,M}$, expressed in °C/min.

Table 3
Parametric optimizations for artificial optimal data generation.

Param.	Meaning	Parameter values (total number of combinations)		
		CCD (429)	FFD (243)	Random (621)
k_r	Racemization rate constant / 10^8	1, 10, 10^2	3.16, 10, $3.16 \cdot 10^2$	[1, 100]
k_s	Secondary nucleation rate constant / 10^8	1, 10, 10^2	3.16, 10, $3.16 \cdot 10^2$	[1, 100]
k_g	Growth rate constant / 10^{12}	5, 27.5, 50	27.5	[1, 50]
t_b	Batch time	6, 9, 12	9	[6,12]
T_{in}	Initial temperature	40, 50, 60	45, 50, 55	[40, 60]
$S.L.$	Total seed load	1, 3, 5	3	[1, 5]
EE_s	Seed EE	10, 50, 90	30, 50, 70	[10, 90]
$L_{r,s}$	Relative seed size*	-1, 0, 1	-1, 0, 1	-1, 0, 1

* -1: small L , large D ; 0: moderately small L , moderately large D , 1: midsize L , midsize D . See the exact specifications in Appendix 3.

2.3. High throughput optimizations and synthetic database generation

Every process simulation could be viewed as a sample in artificial data generation. However, operating under optimal conditions is highly desired. Finding those solutions is solved using process optimization.

Every optimum is subject to goals, constraints, and model parameters. Here we involve six sub-objectives (O_i), specific to the SOAT in CWM, and combine them into a single objective with corresponding weight factors (w_i):

$$O(X) = \sum_{i=1}^6 w_i O_i \quad (11)$$

The sub-objectives are summarized in Table 1. Accordingly, the quantiles of the volume-based product distribution are used as product size descriptors, namely, the D_{10} , D_{50} , D_{90} , and the width of the

distribution (the span, expressed from these quantiles). This simplification is not a limitation of the method. It was made as the named quantiles often hold the necessary particle size information, and reducing the full CSD to its averaged values improves the clarity of presentation of the results. Given the varied parameters, the relative contribution of sub-objectives changes from optimization to optimization. That said, efforts were made using preliminary optimizations to set the weight factors, such as the O_1 has the highest contribution (let this be 100%), O_2 and O_3 be ~10–20%, and the relative importance of $O_3 - O_5$ be comparable but smaller than O_2 and O_3 .

The recirculation rate is kept constant in all simulations for simplicity. The decision variables are the cooling and milling profiles. The starting and final temperatures are fixed, and four intermediate temperatures are optimized (T_i), involving as independent decision variables the sampling instances ($t_{T,i}$) at which T_i are defined. These four intermediate points allow up to two T -cycles. The final milling rate is fixed to zero, whereas the initial, and three intermediate milling rates (ω_i), as well as the time stamps for the three intermediate milling rates ($t_{\omega,i}$) are optimized. Linear interpolation is applied between the discrete temperature and milling points in all simulations. The decision variable vector (X) takes the form:

$$X = (T_1, \dots, T_4, t_{T,1}, \dots, t_{T,4}, \omega_1, \dots, \omega_3, t_{\omega,1}, \dots, t_{\omega,4}) \quad (12)$$

The decision variables (X_i) are scaled (x_i), using as scale factors their initial guesses ($X_{i,in}$):

$$x_i = \frac{X_i}{X_{i,in}} \quad (13)$$

Hence, the scaled initial guess becomes a vector of ones. Table 2 summarizes the bounds and constraints applied in the optimization. Notably, the product quality (EE and particle sizes) are not constrained, which, technically, could have been and should have been for some practical applications. The reason is the following. The optimized product properties are expected to move in a wide interval in the broad domain of the investigated kinetic and process conditions. Hence, the constraints would lead to many infeasible solutions unless the optimization space, including batch times, the flexibility of temperature, and milling profiles, is extended.

Eight key parameters were varied in the optimizations, out of which five are process parameters (freely adjustable by the operator), and three are kinetic constants, which reflect the dynamic system behavior. The former group gives the optimal operation under different operator choices. Given that the kinetic constants were moved in a wide but realistic range, adding the latter ensures database validity in a broad practical domain. The seed size, load, and EE domains cover the typical experimental ranges. It is more difficult to find typical initial temperatures and batch times as these are practically adjusted based on the kinetics to match the design objectives. Still, within the design space, the shorter batch is preferred for productivity and the higher initial concentration for better yields. The 6–12 h batch time and 40–60 °C initial temperature range may be reasonable for industrially relevant cooling crystallization processes. The crystallization kinetics was set based on the work of [3], except for the secondary nucleation rate. The secondary nucleation rate parameters were adjusted such as to result in physically reasonable rates.

Three strategies were applied to combine these eight parameters, as summarized in Table 3. First, a central composite design (CCD) was executed, resulting in 429 parameter combinations. After evaluating these results, a five-dimensional full factorial design (FFD) was created for the variables that appeared to be the most influential on the selected outputs. Finally, a large number of random combinations were made to ensure quasi-continuous mapping of the input parameter space.

Since there is no information on the convexity of the objective function for the optimization task, we used the covariance matrix adaptation-evolutionary algorithm (CMA-ES) [16]. The evolutionary

Fig. 3. Distribution of the shear integrals of the optimal operations that involve milling and the selection of threshold shear integral for milling and milling-free operations.

algorithms, in general, are based on population generation in each iteration. The main idea is the “survival” of the fittest members of the population. This goal is achieved using the fittest members as “parents” for the next generation (iteration). The fitness function is assigned with the objective function. CMA-ES uses as population generation a random sampling from a multivariate normal distribution. The normal distribution parameters (mean values and covariance matrix) are recalculated in each step to move the multivariate normal probability distribution toward the optimal or closed optimal solution. The repeated population generation gives the possibility of escaping from local optima. In our case, the objective function Eq. (11) depends on the decision variables Eq. (12). The optimization took a few hours, depending on the parameters, e.g., batch time, on an Intel i5 10,400 CPU, 32 GB DDR4 memory. Two machines ran ten optimizations in parallel (given the six-core CPU).

2.4. Data mining for knowledge extraction

Three investigations were executed: (i) classification for device selection; (ii) regression analysis for product property prediction; (iii) explanatory analyses for local interpretation of ML results. Before the training, the inputs were scaled and divided into three groups: 80 % was assigned for model training, 10 % for model selection, and 10 % for final testing.

Classification. Two classifications are executed: for the existence of T -cycle in the optimal operation and the necessity of milling. Both take as inputs the five processes and three kinetic parameters. The calculations are executed in Python in two stages: all classification models (29) of the scikit-learn library were applied with their default hyperparameters as a quick screening, then the most promising model (based on validation performance) was fine-tuned. The scikit-learn is an open-source Python library incorporating numerous predictive data analysis techniques [26]. The classification performance is characterized based on the Area Under the receiver operating characteristic Curve (AUC) score. AUC is a single scalar value that measures the overall performance of binary classifiers [15]. An AUC value of 1 indicates perfect, whereas 0.5 corresponds to random classification.

Regression analysis. Regression analysis was performed to predict the product EE, mean size (D_{50}) and the span of the distribution. Similarly to the classification training, all regression models of the scikit-learn (42)

were applied as a preliminary screening; the most promising model was fine-tuned. Notably, artificial neural networks (ANNs) beyond the scikit-learn’s perceptron model were deployed and subject to hyperparameter optimization using Google Brain’s TensorFlow library. Feedforward backpropagation NNs were applied involving one, two, and three hidden layers, varying the activation function systematically (using rectifying linear units, linear units, and sigmoidal activations). A grid search method adjusted the learning rate and the number of neurons in each layer. Furthermore, neuron dropout and pruning were applied as more advanced strategies to reduce the chance of overfitting. Still, in this case, ANNs showed inferior performance to tree-based methods, which the relatively small sample size may explain.

Shapley additive explanations. Lloyd Shapley proposed the method for obtaining Shapley values in game theory for the following problem. N players collectively obtain a reward to be distributed amongst the players according to their individual contributions. The Shapley value of each player equals this contribution. This idea was transferred to the ML community as a tool for explaining feature contribution to the regression result [30]. Later, new methods are presented with improved computational performance for calculating Shapley value [22]. This has twofold importance. It can be used locally regarding each sample and globally, considering the whole dataset to explain the contribution of a given feature. For a given sample data, the Shapley value of a feature i shows how this feature explains the difference between the predicted value corresponding to this sample and the mean of all predictions. The overall importance of the feature i is the average of Shapley values of the i^{th} feature over all samples.

For the classification and regression, Random Forest (RF) and Xgboost were the best among the evaluated models. Both are based on decision trees. RF was introduced in [17] and developed in [5]. It is an ensemble learning method that uses multiple trees. The main idea is the subsampling of the dataset and also the feature set and fitting decision trees. RFs are more robust than a single decision tree. Xgboost is a special type of gradient-boosting algorithm [8,12]. Gradient boosting fits a sequence of trees to the sequence of residuals. Xgboost is a regularized version of gradient boosting, which is, therefore, considerably faster.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Crystallization or integrated system?

While grouping the samples based on T -cycles’ existence in the optimal temperature profile is straightforward, the with or without milling decision could be clearer. Indeed, in some cases the optimal milling rate remained zero throughout the simulation. However, in some cases, a small milling was involved, but from a practical standpoint to a negligible degree. Two reasons are found for these cases: (i) the mill is operated at a rotation speed that is significantly below the normal range, and (ii) the milling rate is sufficiently large, but the duration is too short of making an effect (i.e., a few seconds). The shear integral is introduced to characterize the overall milling intensity, defined as:

$$N_{sh,i} = \int_0^{t_p} N_{sh} dt \quad (14)$$

The distribution of the shear integral is illustrated in Fig. 3. The histogram is bimodal: there is a peak in 10^{10} – 10^{12} s^{-1} , and another in 10^{13} – 10^{15} s^{-1} range. The peaks can be separated with a threshold of 10^{12} s^{-1} . From a physical perspective, the typical shear rates are 10^9 – 10^{11} s^{-2} [21]. Hence, a relatively short (e.g., a few seconds long) typical mill operation translates to shear integrals of 10^{10} – 10^{12} s^{-1} . Given the recirculation flow rate, these shear integrals would hardly impact the product properties remarkably. The chosen threshold would sort these points correctly into the “negligible milling” area in the plot of

Fig. 4. Typical optimal operating profiles. a) synchronized integrated operation; b) the optimal milling rate remains nearly zero, and the CWM degenerates to batch crystallization. The shared parameters: $T_i = 40$ °C; $t_b = 6$ h; Seed load = 1 %, seed EE = 10 %, $k_r = 10^{10}$. The lines are only guides to the eye.

Table 4

Optimal product properties of the two processes presented in Fig. 4.

	a)	b)
Product EE (%)	95.9	1.4
D_{10} (μm)	50.6	12.5
D_{50} (μm)	70.3	27.9
D_{90} (μm)	85.1	42.4
span	2.04	0.94

Fig. 3. Thus, the effects of milling in samples belonging to the left-hand side peak are considered negligible. The milling may not have been set to zero due to the sensitivity of decision variables characterizing the milling profile in low milling domains.

If $N_{sh,i}$ is under the threshold, the problem gets the label “0”; otherwise, CWM is utilized, marked with label “1”.

Table 5

Summary of parametric optimization results.

		Number of samples (#)	Share, total share (%)
With milling	Total	793	100, 61.1
	No T-cycle	252	31.8, 19.5
	One T-cycle	496	62.5, 38.4
	Two T-cycle	45	5.7, 3.5
	Product EE > 70 %	267	33.7, 20.7
	%		
Without milling	Total	500	100, 38.7
	No T-cycle	381	76.2, 29.5
	One T-cycle	117	23.4, 9.0
	Two T-cycle	2	0.40, 0.16
	Product EE > 70 %	84	16.8, 6.49
	%		

3.2. Summary of optimization results

Global optimizations were performed that simultaneously provide the optimal operating profiles and the associated product EE and particle properties. Two representative results are depicted in Fig. 4, which differ in only the three parameters displayed on the figures. In spite of this, remarkably different operating profiles are obtained. Meanwhile, in the a) subfigure, there are two T-cycles, in the b) subfigure, the well-known parabolic cooling shows up. Furthermore, in case a), there is intense milling during the first T-cycle, whereas no milling is involved in the b) case. Even though constant flowrate recirculation is applied regardless on mill operation, it is a fair assumption that in the case b) the integrated system degenerates to a batch crystallizer.

The product properties belonging to the operations of Fig. 4 are listed in Table 4, which explains the vastly different operating profiles. Since the product EE in the b) is small, the first sub-objective (see Table 1) is negligible. Hence, the objective function is improved via the rest of the terms, including particle properties, minimizing the T-cycles, and mill usage. It is difficult to explain why the product EEs differ so much, as the racemization rates are identical. Indeed, the nucleation and growth kinetics, and the seed sizes differed. The influence and contribution of individual inputs are unclear.

Table 5 summarizes the synthetic database. It divides the result into two groups based on the existence of wet milling. Nearly 61 % of cases involve milling, which confirms the hypothesis that CWMs are effective platforms for SOAT. It is enlightening to look at the share of cases in which the product EE exceeded an arbitrarily set 70 % threshold: in the CWM group, it is 33.7 %, nearly twice as high as in the crystallization-only group (16.8). Another remarkable difference is that the share of samples involving two T-cycles is an order of magnitude higher (5.7 vs 0.4 %) in the CWM group. Most CWM samples involved one T-cycle (62.5 %), in sharp contrast with the crystallization-only group, dominated by the no T-cycle samples (76.2 %).

Fig. 5 illustrates the product EE distributions, the primary optimization objectives, in the four operation classes. Fig. 5a indicates that with wet milling but without simultaneous T-cycling the product EE shows a bimodal distribution but with lower values (remaining under 50 %). In contrast, when the optimal operation involves T-cycling, the product EEs are considerably higher, with a stark peak in the 96–100 % bin. The crystallization-only system shows similar trends, with a better separation: if T-cycles are not involved, the product EEs are generally less than 20 %, but a considerable number of samples involving T-cycles deliver nearly 100 % enantio-purity.

Even though some degree of output prediction can be made based on the inputs and process understanding, it is extremely difficult to understand such large dimensional problems governed by nonlinear physics and chemistry. Fortunately, for ML algorithms, the more data, the better.

Fig. 5. Distribution of product EEs in the four operation classes: a) CWM systems with and without involving *T*-cycling; b) crystallization-only systems with and without *T*-cycling.

Table 6

Classification performance on the prediction of equipment selection (integrated crystallization and wet milling or crystallization-only) and whether *T*-cycling should or should not be considered.

	<i>T</i> -cycling?	Milling?
Algorithm	Xgboost	Xgboost
Number of trees	1300	100*
Validation AUC	0.902	0.880
Test AUC	0.877	0.910

*reached the boundary of the hyperparameter optimization.

3.3. Data-mining results and discussions

Firstly, all (eight) inputs are used to predict two discrete outputs: the existence of *T*-cycling in the optimal crystallization operation (yes or no), and the implication of wet mill (yes or no). Table 6 presents the trained models with the adjusted hyperparameters, the validation (used

for model selection and hyperparameter tuning) and the test performance. The Xgboost performed the best for both cases, but the number of trees was significantly different. This manifests in little over-training, as the test score is worse than the validation score when the number of estimators is high. Nevertheless, an AUC score >0.85 is often considered an excellent classification, which threshold was exceeded in all cases.

Fig. 6a and c provide a visual representation of classification performance: the squares in the first diagonal are the misclassifications, whereas the top left and bottom right are the correct classifications. Meanwhile, there are some misclassifications, the ratio between the correctly and wrongly classified samples is good in the test set (114:16 for *T*-cycling, and 118:12 for wet milling). Subfigures 6b and 6d are the SHAP diagrams for the *T*-cycling and wet milling classifications. Fig. 6b interprets the with or without *T*-cycling decision locally where “0” label is for no *T*-cycling. Being in the top line, the racemization rate strongly influences the decision and indicates that slow racemization seeks crystallization only. Still, since the green and intermediate colors are mixed, the effect of the racemization rate saturates over a threshold reaction rate. The subsequent three most important inputs are the initial conditions. The batch time has the weakest influence, and the growth and nucleation rates have a moderate effect. It is somewhat unexpected that the liquid-phase reaction rate drives the choice of wet milling (Fig. 6d): the lowest racemization rates would push the system to crystallization only, whereas moderate and high reaction rates seek integrated systems. An explanation can be the penalization terms of the optimization objective functions: if no significant enantiomer excess can be reached, the milling is turned off. The relative seed size and initial temperature are the second and third most important inputs: high relative seed size difference (−1 discrete value) and low initial temperatures favor the implication of the mill. The growth rate constant is the least important parameter, but the nucleation rate seems to be the four most influential. In line with expectations, slow nucleation seeks milling: the small particles enhance the de-racemization, and the milling fills the gap in fine particle production for slow nucleation. Overall, inputs have a more balanced influence on the milling or no milling classification, making the mill selection a more complex decision.

A practical limitation of the afore-described classification is the (non)existence of the kinetic parameters: the racemization, nucleation, and growth rates are system specific, thus, have to be measured. Meanwhile, determining the racemization rate is relatively simple; determining the nucleation and growth kinetics is an Achilles’ heel, requiring advanced experimentation and calculations [36]. Fortunately, the relative importance of these constants is low in both classifiers. A new set of classification models was built, removing these parameters from the inputs and relying on the remaining five process parameters and the racemization rate (Table 7). Accordingly, for with or without milling the RF, whereas for *T*-cycling or not classification, the Xgboost gave the best performance. The calibration and test AUCs are lower than those presented in Table 6, and both remain in the excellent classification range (AUC >0.85). Comparing the test performances of Tables 6 and 7, the accuracy drop in Table 7 is greater for the milling or no milling classification. The SHAP diagrams of Fig. 6 explain this observation: two weak inputs were removed from the *T*-cycling, whereas the nucleation rate appeared to be more important in the milling decision.

The natural question arises at this point: having the input parameters and the equipment selection and process design knowledge, what is the expected product property profile? How should the process parameters be tweaked to realize the target profile robustly? To keep the simplicity without losing the generality, three industrially critical outputs are considered: the EE, the mean size (D_{50} , the two populations combined), and the width (span) of the product crystals. Two regression analyses are carried out:

- Case A: we take the eight parameters and the true values of the milling and *T*-cycling classes.

Fig. 6. Summary of classification models. a) and b) confusion plot and the SHAP diagram for the *T*-cycling or no question. b) and c) confusion plot and the SHAP diagram for the CWM vs crystallization-only system.

Table 7

Classification performance without involving as inputs the hard-to-measure and less influential nucleation and growth parameters.

	<i>T</i> -cycling?	Milling?
Algorithm	Xgboost	RF
Number of trees	100*	200
Minimum number of samples per leaf**	–	4
Validation AUC	0.886	0.867
Test AUC	0.862	0.877

*reached the boundary of the hyperparameter optimization **not an adjustable parameter in the applied Xgboost regressor.

Table 8

Regression algorithms and Pearson correlation coefficients (*R*) between the actual and regressed outputs for Case A and Case B cases.

	Case A			Case B		
	EE	<i>D</i> ₅₀	Span	EE	<i>D</i> ₅₀	Span
Algorithm	Xgboost	Xgboost	Xgboost	RF	Xgboost	RF
Number of trees	1500*	200	100*	1400	100*	400
Minimum number of samples per leaf*	–	–	–	3	–	3
Validation <i>R</i>	0.991	0.966	0.959	0.989	0.631	0.825
Test <i>R</i>	0.991	0.953	0.928	0.973	0.545	0.835

*reached the boundary of the hyperparameter optimization **not an adjustable parameter in the applied Xgboost regressor.

- Case B: the hard-to-measure nucleation and growth kinetic parameters are excluded compared to Case A.

According to Table 8, the Xgboost regression is particularly successful for this problem. The number of estimators moves in a broad range between 100 and 1500. The Pearson correlation does not show a significant performance degradation resulting from excluding the kinetic inputs, except for the Case B *D*₅₀ regression. Leaving the crystallization kinetics out from the inputs hampers the crystal size prediction accuracy the most. Surprisingly, the span prediction is less affected, and the accuracy of EE calculation is barely affected. This last observation is fascinating for two reasons: from a theoretical perspective, de-racemization results from stereoselective crystal growth, yet the optimal operation provides sufficient information for a regression model. From an applied perspective, the *enantio*-purity can be predicted accurately without crystallization kinetic information (see Table A1).

Fig. 7 depicts the parity plots and the SHAP diagrams for Case A regressions, where strong correlations are revealed (Appendix 4 presents the Case B plots). It is enlightening to analyze the SHAP diagrams: the racemization rate is the most influential input on the product EE. This may be controversial, as racemization brings the system to equilibrium. An explanation is that the selective removal of an enantiomer creates the imbalance in the liquid phase that drives the racemization, allowing faster reproduction from the antipode. A difficult-to-explain result is that the racemization rate is also the most influential input of the product span prediction. This may be related to the supersaturation production effect of the chemical reaction. The marginal EE prediction degradation in Case B is explained by Fig. 7b, where the nucleation and growth rates have a weak influence. The relative importance of *L* and *D*

Fig. 7. Summary of product property profile prediction in Case A regression. Upper line: product EE, middle line: product D_{50} and bottom line: product span prediction and SHAP explanations.

seed sizes is within the top three in all cases, meaning that careful seed design is crucial to operating a SOAT well. An unexpected result is that the batch time has a weak effect (it is at the bottom of the D_{50} and span list, with a relatively weak effect on the product EE). This decouples the productivity from the attainable product quality under optimal operating conditions, which situation has not been documented yet. The importance of productivity can hardly be overestimated in industrial environments. Therefore, this underscores the benefits of optimal design and paves the way for tremendous productivity enhancements in a well-designed process. Only the T -cycling highly influences the product EE prediction regarding categorical inputs. No other categorical inputs can be found between the top priority inputs.

According to the SHAP analyses, the nucleation and growth kinetics have a relatively weak influence, except for the mean product crystal size prediction. This may be an unexpected outcome for practitioners that needs further explanation. At this point, it is to be reiterated that the ML models were trained based on optimal process operations. That is, the dynamic profiles of temperatures and milling rates were found by optimization to result in a minimal aggregated objective function value, representing a good product and process behavior. This leads to interactions between the kinetic and process conditions. For an example, let us consider the SHAP diagrams of Fig. 5: slower nucleation seeks T -cycling and wet-milling. The former enhances the nucleation by fast supersaturation generation, whereas the latter can produce small

Fig. 8. Summary of the sequential hybrid mechanistic modeling and data-driven framework proposed and applied successfully in this study.

Fig. A1. The modeled system considers a three-stage external wet mill.

particles, acting as an induced nucleator. In the knowledge that stereoselective secondary nucleation is known to enhance de-racemization, it is enlightening to realize that the process is set to (to some extent) make up for the kinetic limitations. Hence, from the optimal results, it may appear like the kinetics has less influence on the product.

4. A meta-analysis to validate the key outcomes

A brief meta-analysis is carried out to cross-check the key conclusions. Successful validation of existing results is a strong indication of the overall validity. This validates the yet-unknown results and is promising for the developed framework.

Table A1

The list of fixed kinetic parameters.

Param.	Meaning	Value
a_0	Solubility model parameter	$9.20 \cdot 10^{-3}$
a_1	Solubility model parameter	$4.43 \cdot 10^{-2}$
a_2	Solubility model parameter	$3.048 \cdot 10^{-2}$
k_p	Primary nucleation rate constant	$7.18 \cdot 10^{25}$
p	Supersaturation exponent of primary nucleation rate	3.41
E_p	Activation energy of primary nucleation rate	$1.035 \cdot 10^5$
s	Supersaturation exponent of secondary nucleation rate	2.5
g	Supersaturation exponent of growth rate	2.47
E_g	Activation energy of growth rate	$7.67 \cdot 10^4$
k_d	Dissolution rate constant	$2.94 \cdot 10^8$
d	Supersaturation exponent of dissolution rate	0.51
E_d	Activation energy of dissolution rate	$5.16 \cdot 10^4$
E_r	Activation energy of racemization rate	$7.5 \cdot 10^4$
k_{br}	Breakage rate constant	$1 \cdot 10^{-10}$
k	Parameter of the breakage selection function	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$
L_{cr}	Critical particle size for crystal breakage	$2 \cdot 10^2$
β	Parameter of the fragment distribution function	0.8
α	Parameter of the fragment distribution function	1

Table A2

Head configurations of the three-stage external wet mill.

Parameter	Name	Value		
		First stage	Second stage	Third stage
D_r	Rotor diameter (mm)	30.1	30.1	30.1
N_S	Number of slots in the stator	9	14	14
N_R	Number of slots in the rotor	20	45	45
d	Gap between the stator and the rotor (mm)	0.15	0.15	0.15

Table A3

Mean and standard deviation of the log-normal distribution describing the seed size distributions in the three cases.

Case	Enantiomer	Mean (μm)	Standard deviation (μm)
-1	L	10	7
	D	115	35
0	L	40	20
	D	80	30
1	L	50	25
	D	50	25

- our models align with the observations that stereoselective secondary nucleation and crystal growth can result in de-racemization, and that can be achieved without agglomeration - formerly named as a potential driver [3].

- since the majority of our optimal processes (61 %) involved milling, and it is a reasonable assumption that in many cases, the mill usage was rejected by the penalization rather than by the lack of ability to improve the product EE, our results overlay with the observation that Viedma ripening is enhanced by milling [38].
- it is known that higher initial EE translates to faster de-racemization [7], or, at a fixed batch-time, higher attainable product EE. According to our SHAP analysis, the seed EE is the third most important input. Some studies create asymmetry in the liquid phase *via* a difference between the concentrations of the enantiomers. We assumed a racemic solution for practical reasons (chemical synthesis leads to racemic mixtures), but the seed composition asymmetry has similar effects.
- optimizing the conditions for the best catalyst performance [37], the catalyst concentration, or catalyst selection [2] were called to

Fig. A2. Summary of product property profile prediction in Case B regressions. Upper line: product EE, middle line: product D_{50} , and bottom line: product span prediction and SHAP explanations.

improve de-racemization. In our analyses, the racemization rate was the most important driver of the product's enantiopurity, supporting the aforementioned studies.

- the effect of seeding was analyzed [4]. The authors found that the faster de-racemization was achieved when the mean sizes of the *D* and *L* seeds were not identical, and one of the two enantiomers was initially in excess in terms of mass. The importance of seed size difference was also demonstrated for batch isothermal de-racemization where Oswald ripening enabled small particles to dissolve [43]. This is supported by our SHAP diagram, where the relative size of seed crystals is the second, and the seed EE (the relative amount of seed enantiomers) is the third most important parameter influencing the product EE.
- in some cases, high enantiopurity was achieved without milling and *T*-cycling (Fig. 5b, green histogram). This behavior is supported by an experimental paper demonstrating that SOAT could be employed for complete de-racemization without temperature cycling [25].

Besides the product EE, the product particle properties were also the subject of our optimization. We could not identify papers dealing simultaneously with racemization and product particle properties. Hence, we will focus on particle size adjustment aspects (see Table A3).

- a modeling paper analyzed the growth, dissolution, and wet milling cycles to control rod-like particles' shape [28]; and a generalized pattern involving one *T*-cycle and early-stage milling was proposed for simultaneous size and shape control [34]. This last pattern was verified experimentally for an active pharmaceutical ingredient [11].
- analyzing the dynamic operating profiles was outside of the scope, yet, according to Table 5, 62.5 % of cases involving milling have one, and a further 5.7 % have two *T*-cycles. The dynamic profiles of Fig. 4a indicate, similarly to the latter citation, that milling is implemented only during the first *T*-cycle.
- most industrial publications apply wet milling as a terminal particle size correction step [21]. The importance of combined milling and crystallization, implemented in this work, was shown to benefit from the crystal surface healing effects of the crystal growth [1].

4.1. Workflow summary and outlook

This study discussed the specific case of a novel combination of mechanistic modeling and data mining for early-stage technology screening and operation-related knowledge extraction. The workflow can be summarized by the following steps, as also presented in Fig. 8:

1. Problem statement. Clearly defining the problem to be solved, with the goals and constraints, is necessary.
2. The technology alternatives or the superstructure believed to incorporate all potential solutions must be provided.
3. The technology alternatives or the superstructure must be described with design-oriented, high-fidelity dynamic physical process models. This may have a high computational burden, which advanced computing infrastructures must address.
4. Parametric global optimizations. The key process and kinetic parameters should be varied in a reasonable interval: the process parameters must cover the domains of interest, whereas kinetic constants must ensure the validity of results in a broad range of realistic dynamic behaviors. This will generate a synthetic database of optimal process behaviors.
5. Application of classification models to predict the best technology option for the given inputs. Application of regression models to predict the continuous outputs.
6. Interpretation and utilization of the results.

All parts of this highly theoretical framework should be executed with practical considerations in mind. For example, the models should be sufficiently detailed to generate realistic databases, but complexity has to be balanced with the computational burden. The computational burden was identified as a significant bottleneck in this case study. Nevertheless, this can be treated with advanced information technology solutions (multicore calculations, more efficient numerical schemes, accelerated warm-start optimizations, etc.). These improvements are necessary to significantly extend the framework, either at a process level or by applying kinetic rate equation libraries. Furthermore, some important model parameters are difficult to measure. One aims to eliminate these from the ML inputs, which can be carried out with greater success if the parameter has a weaker influence on the outputs. The framework has virtually limitless extension potential. For application, however, some theoretical and practical considerations exist (Fig. A2):

1. Readily available kinetic and thermodynamic models have to exist for the microscopic physical-chemical mechanisms.
2. The process simulations have to be fast enough for high-throughput optimizations.
3. Specific modeling software is necessary for broader industrial use to create the synthetic database quickly.

5. Conclusions

This work presented a novel, fully *in-silico* framework for simultaneous early-stage technology screening and process and product design, through the case study of the second-order asymmetric transformation of enantiomers in integrated crystallization-wet milling platforms. The technique exploits the predictive power of first principle models suitable to capture the physical roots of the phenomena with sufficiently high fidelity. Then, a parametric study varies the key process and kinetic parameters, resulting in a broad space of process conditions and dynamic system behaviors. A global optimization is deployed to find the operation and the associated product property profile for each process and kinetic parameter combination. The synthetic database involved nearly 1300 optimal solutions, from which ~60 % involved significant mill operation and ~50 % involved at least one *T*-cycle. Subsequently, data science techniques were applied to extract design and operation-relevant knowledge from the database. We illustrated that technology selection between two competing alternatives could be predicted excellently with tree-based classifiers (AUC score exceeding 0.85 on the test set), and the product EE, D_{50} , and span was predicted well (Pearson correlations exceeding 0.95). The results aligned perfectly with existing literature, with some important discoveries. Under optimal operation, the batch time does not significantly influence the product's purity or particle properties, which decouples the productivity from the quality within the investigated domain. Furthermore, the classifications and regressions worked well without hard-to-measure crystallization kinetic information, except for the product crystal size prediction. The results also demonstrated how machine learning could support process development by extracting valuable knowledge from physical model-based process simulations.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix

Appendix 1 The macroscopic model-equations

It is assumed that the circulation flow rate (F) is constant throughout the process, as illustrated in Fig. A1.

Assuming constant working volume, the mean residence time (τ) is constant, and proportional to the operating volumes:

$$\tau_i = \frac{V_i}{F} \quad (\text{A1})$$

The transport delay in the pipe is neglected. With this in mind, the crystallizer and wet mills are described as continuous well-mixed tank systems.

Modeling the crystallizer

For the description of particle population, the monovariate size density function $n(L, t)$ is introduced, which gives the number of crystals within the $[L, L + dL]$ interval per unit volume of suspension in t time. Assuming perfect mixing and homogenous suspension temperature, the PBE governing the time evolution of the size density function of i enantiomer in the crystallizer takes the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial n_{c,i}(L, t)}{\partial t} + G_i \frac{\partial n_{c,i}(L, t)}{\partial L} &= B_i \delta(L - L_n) + \frac{1}{\tau_c} [n_{m,3,i}(L, t) - n_{c,i}(L, t)], \text{ if } \sigma_i \geq 0 \\ \frac{\partial n_{c,i}(L, t)}{\partial t} - D_i \frac{\partial n_{c,i}(L, t)}{\partial L} &= \frac{1}{\tau_c} [n_{m,3,i}(L, t) - n_{c,i}(L, t)], \text{ if } \sigma_i < 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A2})$$

where $n_{m,3,i}(L, t)$ denotes the third stage of the wet mill that feeds the crystallizer. The initial and boundary conditions are:

$$n_c(L, t) = n_{c,0}(L)$$

$$\lim_{L \rightarrow \infty} n_c(L, t) = 0 \quad (\text{A3})$$

The material balance, where the right hand side considers the crystallization, chemical reaction, and recirculation, respectively, takes the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dc_{c,i}}{dt} &= -\rho_c k_V 10^{18} \left[3G_i \int_0^{L_{\max}} L^2 n_c(L, t) dL + B_i L_n^3 \right] + r_i + \frac{1}{\tau_c} (c_{m,3,i} - c_{c,i}), \text{ if } \sigma_i \geq 0 \\ \frac{dc_{c,i}}{dt} &= 3D_i \rho_c k_V 10^{-18} \int_0^{L_{\max}} L^2 n_c(L, t) dL + r_i + \frac{1}{\tau_c} (c_{m,3,i} - c_{c,i}), \text{ if } \sigma_i < 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A4})$$

where the initial conditions are the initial concentrations of the enantiomers.

Modeling the wet mill

The PBE for the wet mill incorporates nucleation, crystal growth and dissolution, and fragmentation of particles, described as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial n_{m,k,i}(L, t)}{\partial t} + G_i \frac{\partial n_{m,k,i}(L, t)}{\partial L} &= B_i \delta(L - L_n) + \frac{1}{\tau_{m,k}} [n_{m,k-1,i}(L, t) - n_{m,k,i}(L, t)] + \int_0^{L_{\max}} b(L|\lambda) n_{m,k,i}(\lambda, t) S(\lambda) d\lambda - S(L) n_{m,k,i}(L, t), \text{ if } \sigma_i \geq 0 \\ \frac{\partial n_{m,k,i}(L, t)}{\partial t} - D_i \frac{\partial n_{m,k,i}(L, t)}{\partial L} &= \frac{1}{\tau_{m,k}} [n_{m,k-1,i}(L, t) - n_{m,k,i}(L, t)] + \int_0^{L_{\max}} b(L|\lambda) n_{m,k,i}(\lambda, t) S(\lambda) d\lambda - S(L) n_{m,k,i}(L, t), \text{ if } \sigma_i < 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A5})$$

where subscript “ k ” stands for the k^{th} stage of the wet mill, with values of 1, 2, and 3. The first stage mill ($k = 1$) receives the feed ($k - 1$) from the crystallizer. Eq. (A5) has initial and boundary conditions given in Eq. (A3).

The mass balance has an identical form to that of Eq. (A4). An energy balance is written to calculate the temperature dynamics of the wet mill. Energy balance was necessary as the wet mills usually do not have internal temperature control, and the energy intake of the mill is significant:

$$\frac{dT_m}{dt} = \frac{\varepsilon_m(\omega)}{c_{p,sol} \rho_{sol}} - \frac{k_V \rho_c R_V H_c}{c_{p,s} \rho_s} + \frac{1}{\tau_m} (T_{m-1} - T_m) \quad (\text{A6})$$

with $T_{wm}(t = 0) = T_{wm,0}$ initial condition. H_c is the latent heat of crystallization, $c_{p,s}$ denotes the specific heat capacity of the solution and ρ_s is the solution density. Mass-weighted averaging was applied to approximate the solution density and specific heat capacity, considering the actual concentration conditions. R_V denotes the overall rate of crystallization or dissolution of both enantiomers, expressed as $R_V = \sum_{i=1}^2 R_{V,i}$

$$\begin{aligned} R_{V,i} &= k_V \rho_c 10^{18} \left[3G_i \int_0^{L_{\max}} L^2 n_{m,k}(L, t) dL + B_i L_n^3 \right], \text{ if } \sigma_i \geq 0 \\ R_{V,i} &= -3D_i k_V \rho_c 10^{-18} \int_0^{L_{\max}} L^2 n_{m,k}(L, t) dL, \text{ if } \sigma_i < 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A7})$$

where the factor of 10^{-18} is to convert the μm units of particle size to metric units of bulk volume. The mean value of turbulence dissipation rate ($\varepsilon_m(\omega)$) in stirred vessels can be calculated as:

$$\varepsilon_m(\omega) = \frac{P_0 \omega^3 D_{r,m}^5}{V_m} \quad (\text{A8})$$

P_0 is the power number, an empirical dimensionless number specific to the impeller.

Appendix 2 Definition of parameters used in the simulation studies

Table A2 lists the configuration of heads in the external wet mill. The practice was followed that a coarse(s) head that mills down the large particles that would clog the fine hears is applied in the first stage, followed by fine(r) heads that are responsible for reaching the desired particle sizes.

Appendix 3 Seed size distribution definition

Appendix 4 Prediction of the product EE, D50, and span via regression analysis and SHAP diagrams for the trained models: Case B plots

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